

Trafficking Girls and Women and its Effect: A Case Study of Manipur

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Abstract:

Human trafficking has become one of the major challenges among all other crimes against women not only in Manipur but all over the world. Surprisingly, it is one of the biggest organized crime after drugs and weapons. Although it remained elusive from the society, there is a rapid increase of trafficking in the state even with the presence of a number of women's vigil groups, civil bodies and others. It can be seen that, no matter where they come from, they all faced common factors such as poverty, conflict, instability, and etc. all in search for a better life. Among which poverty is the most common factor of it. Many of them are lured on the pretext of providing jobs, especially, in foreign countries like Thailand, Singapore, etc. These trafficked victims are being exploited physically and mentally. For those who escaped are left damage (permanently) like social stigma, various negative impacts on their lives including health and others. This paper will provide a general study about trafficking especially on women in Manipur. It will bring out the effect(s) on these trafficked women on social level and also will discuss the impact it has on its victims.

Key Words: Women, Trafficking, Health Issues, Manipur, Exploitation, Prostitution

Introduction

Manipur, a state in the north-eastern part of India share international border with Myanmar which has, now, become a hub for human trafficking. The state has become one of the source, transit and destination for women and child trafficking, especially for sexual exploitation, prostitution and child labour.¹ Most of them especially girls and women are trafficked for prostitution and for bonded labour to Thailand, Singapore, Malaysia, and Japan as they are in high demand of their Mongolian look² via Myanmar³ and in India to Chennai,⁴ Meghalaya,⁵ Tamil Nadu⁶, Bangalore, Delhi, Mumbai and other places.

Before going any further, it is important to understand what human trafficking is. According to Article 3 of the UN Protocol, trafficking in persons is define as “*the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring or receipt of persons, by means of the threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of the abuse of power or of a position of vulnerability or of the giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person, for the purpose of exploitation*”. Exploitation here shall include, at a minimum, “*the exploitation of the prostitution of others or other form of sexual exploitation, forced labour or services, slavery or practices similar to slavery, servitude or the removal of organs*”. Thus trafficking can be conceptualise in, first, the transportation of a person; second, force, fraud, or coercion; and, finally, exploitation. In Indian context, the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013 amended section 370 of the Indian Penal Code defined trafficking as whoever, for the purpose of exploitation (a) recruits, (b) transports, (c) harbours, (d) transfer or (e) receives, a person or persons, by – first- using threat, or secondly- using force, or any other form of coercion, or thirdly, - by abduction, or fourthly- by practicing fraud, or deception or fifthly - by abuse of power, or sixthly- by inducement, including the giving or

¹ Ministry of women and child development, Government of India report on Child Trafficking in the Indo-Myanmar region: A Case Study in Manipur by Shri S. Saratkumar Sharma, Chairperson, Manipur Commission for Protection of Child Rights Ref. no. 54/1/2016/MCPR, dated 12/02/2016

² Das, Eli Kumari (2016) Human trafficking in North Eastern region: A Study with Global Perspectives, *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 21(5): 08-11. Also see Ministry of women and child development, Government of India report on Child Trafficking in the Indo-Myanmar region: A Case Study in Manipur by Shri S. Saratkumar Sharma, Chairperson, Manipur Commission for Protection of Child Rights Ref. no. 54/1/2016/MCPR, dated 12/02/2016

³ The India Express (2017) Three human traffickers arrested in Manipur, 3 Women Rescued dated 03/09/2017

⁴ 2 Women traffickers arrested in Manipur dated 03/09/2017

⁵ Leivon, Jimmy (2016) Human Trafficking on the rise in State: Kerala among other States Seeking Verification of 20 Children from Manipur, Imphal Free Press dated 01/08/2016

⁶ Leivon, Jimmy (2016) Human Trafficking on the rise in State: Kerala among other States Seeking Verification of 20 Children from Manipur, Imphal Free Press dated 01/08/2016

receiving of payments or benefits, in order to achieve the consent of any person having control over the person recruited, transported, harboured, received, commits the offence of trafficking.

Causes of human trafficking in Manipur

It is learnt that human trafficking occurred across the globe and they happen to share similar causes if not all. According to one article by Eli Kumari Das, there are economic, social and political causes which include poverty, economic inequality, migration, unemployment, climate change, environmental degradation or depression, gender inequality, violence against women and girls, increasing demand for cheap labour in the construction, agriculture sector, mining, poor social protection, corruption inside the country and international level, terrorism, war, increased armed conflicts, etc.⁷ In addition to the above, in a report, in Manipur, the reason includes ethnic conflict, armed conflict, recruitment of children as child soldiers, lack of awareness, lack of communication, poor road connectivity, insurgency, opening of the Trans-Asian Highway, lack of prosecution and conviction of culprits, failure of state mechanism and many more.⁸

Trafficking in Manipur

Trafficking in Manipur has been on the rise although this issue remains elusive in the society. The first case of Human Trafficking in Manipur was reported back in 2005.⁹ The most affected areas are those areas affected by conflict and poverty especially in rural and hilly regions of Tamenglong, Ukhrul, Chandel, Churachandpur and Senapati.¹⁰ It is seen that Christian community tops the chart of victims of human trafficking followed by the Muslim community in the State.¹¹ In a report by the Social Welfare Department (of Manipur), the year from 2008 to 2012, there was recorded a total of 379 cases of human trafficking. In another report by the NGO-Women Action for Development, there were 251 cases of violence against women in 2012

⁷ Das, Eli Kumari (2016) Human trafficking in North Eastern region: A Study with Global Perspectives, *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 21(5): 08-11.

⁸ Ministry of women and child development, Government of India report on Child Trafficking in the Indo-Myanmar region: A Case Study in Manipur by Shri S. Saratkumar Sharma, Chairperson, Manipur Commission for Protection of Child Rights Ref. no. 54/1/2016/MCPR, dated 12/02/2016

⁹ 3 girls from Borayangbi of Bishnupur District and Hatta Golapati of Imphal East District were rescued from Tuhilal Airport by Leivon, Jimmy (2016) Human Trafficking on the rise in State: Kerala among other States Seeking Verification of 20 Children from Manipur, Imphal Free Press dated 01/08/2016

¹⁰ Ministry of women and child development, Government of India report on Child Trafficking in the Indo-Myanmar region: A Case Study in Manipur by Shri S. Saratkumar Sharma, Chairperson, Manipur Commission for Protection of Child Rights Ref. no. 54/1/2016/MCPR, dated 12/02/2016

¹¹ Leivon, Jimmy (2016) Human Trafficking on the rise in State: Kerala among other States Seeking Verification of 20 Children from Manipur, Imphal Free Press dated 01/08/2016

alone of which 78 were cases of trafficking¹². In Manipur most of the victims are minors, women and girls, although, there are no accurate figure.

The aftermath/Effects of Trafficking

Many of the victims of trafficking suffered from mental and physical abuse. Traffickers used different techniques and methods to lure them. Some on the pretext of job opportunity, training etc. they control their victims using different coercive means such as sexual abuse, taking their passports, leaving few or no option to return home, verbal abuse, mental torture etc. For those who are fortunate enough to be rescued or escaped, they are faced with psychological trauma and social stigma. It is seen in the Indian context that many of victims are not seen as victims but as an accused by our society. Parents are unable to accept their ward or child leading to more mental abuse on the victim.

Government's Effort to Combat Trafficking

The State Government has taken up many steps to combat trafficking. Department like Social Welfare, Government of Manipur has rescued and repatriated 530 number of children (in 2008-2016). They have also provided rehabilitation and reintegration programme.¹³ There are number of NGOs, Women's Vigil Groups, Civil Bodies, Child Welfare Committee (CWC), Manipur Commission for Protection of Child Rights (MCPCR) and also the State Government have higher recruitment in the police department¹⁴ for combating this crime. Not only the State but many other states have shown interest to tackle this very problem. To name the Indigenous Women and Children Foundation (IWCF), Dimapur has shown its interest in helping to solve this issue.

The Indian Constitution, too, prohibits trafficking in any form. According to the Indian Constitution, Article no. 23 (1) Provides that, 'trafficking in human beings are prohibited and any contravention of this prohibition shall be an offence and punishable. In Article no. 39 (1) imposes duty on the state to direct its policy towards saving 'that children are given opportunities and facilities to develop in a healthy manner and in condition of freedom and dignity and

¹² Sharma, Sarojkumar K. (2012) Manipur grapples with rising number of crimes against women accessed date 15/09/2018

¹³ Ministry of women and child development, Government of India report on Child Trafficking in the Indo-Myanmar region: A Case Study in Manipur by Shri S. Saratkumar Sharma, Chairperson, Manipur Commission for Protection of Child Rights Ref. no. 54/1/2016/MCPDR, dated 12/02/2016

¹⁴ Sharma, Sarojkumar K. (2012) Manipur grapples with rising number of crimes against women accessed date 15/09/2018

children and youth are protected against exploitation...' The immoral Traffic Preventing Act 1956 is the main legal instrument against the trafficking of human being in the country. In 1998, the Indian Prime minister approved a National Plan of Action to combat trafficking and commercial sexual exploitation of women and children.

Conclusion

From the above, it can be concluded that trafficking has been on the rise in Manipur even after Government's help to combat it. Number of girls and women are falling into the trap. It is important for all the society to be aware of this crime and help one another to tackle this problem.

Recommendations

Preventing trafficking of girls and women requires a multifaceted approach involving government action, community involvement, education, and support services. Here are five measures that can help address this issue:

Legislation and Law Enforcement: Strengthening laws against human trafficking and implementing stringent penalties for offenders is crucial. Law enforcement agencies need to be trained to effectively identify, investigate, and prosecute cases of trafficking. Additionally, cross-border cooperation and coordination between law enforcement agencies can help disrupt trafficking networks.

Awareness and Education: Educating girls and women about the tactics traffickers use and empowering them with knowledge about their rights and available support services can help prevent them from becoming victims. Public awareness campaigns can also help raise awareness among communities about the dangers of trafficking and how to recognize and report suspicious activities.

Support Services: Providing comprehensive support services, including shelters, counseling, legal assistance, and vocational training, for survivors of trafficking is essential for their recovery and reintegration into society. These services should be accessible, culturally sensitive, and tailored to the specific needs of survivors.

Poverty Alleviation and Economic Empowerment: Addressing the root causes of trafficking, such as poverty, inequality, and lack of economic opportunities, is crucial. Initiatives that provide vocational training, microfinance opportunities, and job placement services can empower girls and women economically, reducing their vulnerability to exploitation.

Community Engagement: Engaging communities in the prevention of trafficking is vital. Community-based organizations, religious leaders, schools, and local authorities can play a significant role in raising awareness, providing support to at-risk individuals, and creating a protective environment for girls and women. Building strong social networks and support systems within communities can help prevent trafficking and support survivors.

Combining these measures with a collaborative approach involving governments, civil society organizations, and international agencies can significantly contribute to preventing trafficking of girls and women.